

The Subjunctive Mood and its Types and Forms, the Use of the Subjunctive Mood

Umirzakov Kodirjon Toyirjonovich¹

¹ PhD, Andijan state institute of foreign languages

Abstract:

As we know mood expresses the speaker's attitude to the reality. The speaker's attitude to the reality may be real or unreal (non-real). It may also be a command, a request, an invitation, etc. Consequently, there are the following 3 types of Mood in English:

1. The Indicative Mood.
2. The Imperative Mood.
3. The Subjunctive Mood.

Keywords: Mood, The Indicative Mood, The Imperative Mood, The Subjunctive Mood, Simple non-perfect, Analytical non-perfect, Simple perfect and Analytical perfect forms, mixed types of the subjunctive mood.

The Indicative Mood expresses the speaker's real attitude to the reality. The Imperative Mood induces a person to do or not to do something. The Subjunctive Mood expresses the speaker's unreal attitude to the reality.

In the Indicative Mood there are 16 tense forms in the Active Voice and 10 tense forms in the Passive Voice. There are no tense forms in the Imperative and in the Subjunctive Moods. There are certain forms of the Subjunctive Mood which coincide with this or that tense form of the Indicative Mood.

Teachers and students consider the Subjunctive Mood to be a difficult grammar theme for learners of the English language. In order to make the explanation of the theme "The Subjunctive Mood" easy we suggest using a new method of teaching the Subjunctive Mood in which the new terms

(*Simple non-perfect, Analytical non-perfect, Simple perfect and Analytical perfect forms*) of the Subjunctive Mood are used instead of the old ones (*Subjunctive I, II, III and IV*).

There are four *grammatical forms* and two *semantic types* of the Subjunctive Mood in English:

A). Grammatical forms of the Subjunctive Mood:

I. Simple non-perfect form. III. Simple Perfect form.

II. Analytical non-perfect form. IV. Analytical perfect form.

B). Semantic types of the Subjunctive Mood:

1) A pure type. 2) A mixed type.

Now we shall present a new method of explaining the grammatical forms and semantic types of the Subjunctive Mood.

A) The use of grammatical forms in pure types of the Subjunctive Mood.

I. Simple non-perfect form.

This type of the Subjunctive Mood coincides with the Past Indefinite (2) and the Past Continuous Tense (5) forms of the Indicative Mood. It may be used both in a Simple sentence and in the Subordinate Clause of a complex sentence. This form expresses unreal condition, wish or desire which refer to the Present or Future and may turn to real under certain case.

Note: In this form the verb *to be* has only one form *were* for all the persons.

e.g. Qani endi men ingliz tilini yaxshi *bilsam* I (2)!

If only I *knew* I (2) English well! I wish I *knew* I (2) English well.

Qani endi men ingliz tilini yaxshi *bila olsam* I (2)!

If only I *could know* English well I (2)! I wish I *could know* I (2) English well.

Qani endi hozir o'rtog'im shu yerda *bo'lsa* I (2)!

If only my friend *were* I (2) here now!

I wish my friend *were* I (2) here now.

Qani endi o'rtog'im hozir shu yerda *o'tirgan bo'lsa* I (5)!

If only my friend *were sitting* I (5) here now!

I wish my friend *were sitting* I (5) here now.

II. Analytical non-perfect form.

This form of the Subjunctive Mood coincides with the Future –in- the Past (13) and the Future Continuous-in-the Past tense (14) forms of the Indicative Mood. It is mainly used in the Principal clause of a complex sentence. This form expresses unreal consequence which refers to the present or future and may turn to real under certain cases.

Agar men Ingliz tilini yaxshi *bilsam* I (2), Amerikaga *borardim* II (13)

If I *knew* I (2) English well, I *should go* II (13) to America.

Agar o'rtog'im hozir shu yerda *bo'lsa* I (2), dars *qilardik* II(13).

If my friend *were* I (2) here now, we *should do* II (13) homework.

Agar o‘rtog‘im hozir shu yerda *o‘tirgan bo‘lsa* I (5), birgalashib dars *qilayotgan bo‘lardik* II (14).

If my friend *were sitting* I (5) here now we *should be doing* II (14) homework together.

Note: When the speaker complains of something *would+inf* may be used in the Subordinate clause of a complex sentence.

e.g. Telefon anchadan buyon jiringlayapdi. Telefonga javob berib qo‘yishsaydi-ya!

The phone has been ringing for a long time. I wish somebody *would answer it* II (13).

III. Simple Perfect form.

This form of the Subjunctive Mood coincides with the Past Perfect (8) and the Past Perfect Continuous tense (11) forms of the Indicative Mood. It may be used both in a simple sentence and in the Subordinate clause of a complex sentence. This form expresses unreal condition, wish or desire which refer to the past and can't turn to real.

e.g. Qani endi men o‘tgan yili Ingliz tilini yaxshi *bilganimda* III (8)!

If only I *had known* III (8) English well last year!

I wish I *had known* III (8) English well last year.

Qani endi o‘rtog‘im kecha shu payt shu yerda *o‘tirgan bo‘lganida* III (11)!

If only my friend *had been sitting* III (11) here at this time yesterday!

I wish my friend *had been sitting* III (11) here at this time yesterday.

IV. Analytical perfect form.

This form of the Subjunctive Mood coincides with the Future-Perfect-in the Past (15) and the Future Perfect Continuous-in-the Past tense (16) forms of the Indicative Mood. It is only used in the Principal clause of a complex sentence. This form expresses unreal consequence which refers to the past and can't turn to real.

Agar men o‘tgan yili shu payt Ingliz tilini yaxshi *bilganimda* III (8),

Amerikaga *ketgan bo‘lardim* IV (15).

If I *had known* III (8) English well at this time last year, I *should have gone* IV (15) to America.

Agar o‘rtog‘im kecha shu payt shu yerda *bo‘lganida* III (8), uy vazifasini birgalashib *qilgan bo‘lardik* IV (15).

If my friend *had been* III (8) here at this time yesterday, we *should have done* IV (15) homework together.

Agar ortog‘im kecha shu payt shu yerda *o‘tirgan bo‘lganida* III (11), birgalashib dars *qilayotgan bo‘lardik* IV (16).

If my friend *had been sitting* III (11) here at this time yesterday we *should have been doing* IV (16) homework together.

Note: The Subjunctive Mood may also be expressed in some other ways.

A) Instead of the Simple non-perfect form of the Subjunctive Mood combination of words “But for” is used.

e.g. Yomg‘ir yog ‘masa I (2), biz toqqa *borardik* II (13).

But for the rain, we *should go* II (13) to the mountains.

Yomg‘ir yog ‘maganida III (8), biz toqqa *borgan bo ‘lardik* IV (15).

But for the rain, we *should have gone* IV (15) to the mountains.

B) In the Simple Perfect form the grammatical Inversion may be used in complex sentences.

e.g. *Had I known* III (8) English well last year I *should have gone* IV (15) to America.

C) Analytical non-perfect form may also have the following structure:

Ketsak *bo ‘lardi* II (13)! It is time we *went off* I (2).

Ishni tugatsak *bo ‘lardi* II (13)! It is time we *finished* I (2) the work!

B) The use of grammatical forms in Mixed types of the Subjunctive Mood.

There are two Mixed types of the Subjunctive Mood in English.

In the first type unreal condition, wish or desire in the subordinate clause of a complex sentence refer to the past while in the principal clause unreal consequence refers to the present or future.

e.g. Agar bemor dorini vaqtida *ichganida* III (8), hozir *tuzalib qolardi* II (13).

If the patient *had taken* III (8) medicine in time, he *would be* II (13) well now.

In the second type unreal condition, wish or desire in the subordinate clause refer to no particular time while in the principal clause unreal consequence refers to the Past.

e.g. Agar u *dangasa bo ‘lmasa* I (2), Universitetga *kirgan bo ‘lardi* IV (15).

If he *were not lazy* I (2), he *would have entered* IV (15) the University.

So, the Subjunctive Mood may be divided into *pure* and *mixed* types .

In a pure type structurally the following models may be formed:

a) I (2 or 5) + II (13 or 14); b) III (8 or 11) + IV (15 or 16).

In the first model both unreal condition, wish or desire and unreal consequence refer only to the Present or Future and under certain cases they can turn to real.

e.g. U hozir shu yerda *bo ‘lsa* (present), men unga *yordam berardim* (present).

If he *were* I (2) here now, I *should help* II (13) him.

U ertaga *kelsa* (future), men unga *yordam berardim* (future).

If he *came* I (2) tomorrow, I *should help* II (13) him.

In the second model both unreal condition, wish or desire and unreal consequence refer to the Past and can't turn to real.

e.g. U kecha shu yerda *bo ‘lganida* (past), men unga *yordam bergan bo ‘lardim* (past).

If he *had been* III (8) here yesterday, I *should have helped* IV (15) him.

In a mixed type the following two models may be formed:

a) III (8) + II (13); b) I (2) + IV (15).

In the first model unreal condition, wish or desire refer to the Past while unreal consequence refers to the Present or Future.

e.g. Agar u maktabda yaxshi o'qiganida III (8), hozir student bo'lardi II (13).

If he *had studied* III (8) at school well, he *would be* II (13) a student now.

In the second model unreal condition, wish or desire refer to no particular time while unreal consequence refers to the Past.

e.g. Agar uning esi yo'q bo'lmasa I (2), sizni xafa qilmagan bo'lardi IV (15). If he *were not silly (stupid)* I (2), he *wouldn't have upset* IV (15) you.

In conclusion it's important to note that we made use of our new method at the English lessons with the Bachelor students, at the Magistracy department and Refreshment courses of the English teachers of Universities, Institutes as well as colleges, lyceums and schools who approved and gave a preference to it.

The list of used literature.

1. Маркова Л.С. Краткий грамматический справочник. Английский язык. – Москва, 1972. – 208 с.
2. V.Vositov (2022). Classification theory of Turkic borrowings. "International journal of world languages" Scientific Journal, Tom-1, 11-14
3. G.Ibragimova (2021). Structural and Semantic Properties of Parenthesis in English Essays. "International Journal of Multireligious Understanding." Scientific Journal, Tom-8, 163-168
4. B.Otajonov, A.Ismoilov (2023) "Nominative field of English and Uzbek means expressing the concept of "Mouth"" Organization Committee-153 p
5. B.Otajonov(2023) "The nominative field of means expressing the concept of "Mouth" in English and Uzbek". "Journal of Language and linguistics" Scientific Journal, Tom-6, 171-183
6. Q.Umirzaqov (2012) "Ellipsis in complex sentences as a grammatical and semantic phenomenon in different languages" Филология мэсэлэлэри, Баку, Озарбайжон Республикаси, Том-6, 321-323
7. I.Abdullayev(2023) "Characteristics of mutual function of parts of speech in English and Uzbek", Евразийский журнал академических исследований, Том-3, 7-10
8. G.Zaynobiddinova(2019) "The fifteen stages of teaching number for pupils", "Science and education in the modern challenges of the xxi century"
9. R.M.Yaqubjonova (2023) "Language and culture in english classrooms: greetings, ways of expressing politeness" Наука и инновация, Том-1, 66-68
10. Sh. Xamraqulova (2024) " Unique features of toponymic slangs in English language" SCHOLAR Tom-2, 87-94
11. M.Abduraimova (2022)"The Importance of Teaching English at Early Age in Pre School-Education" Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices, Tom-6, 55-60
12. D.Tuxtasinova(2022) "How to teach english language medical engineering specialty students" International Scientific Conference" Innovative Trends In Science, Practice And Education" Tom-1, 157-162

13. N.Boltaboyeva, N.Latipova (2022) “National And Cultural Variety Of Phraseological Unit Of The English Language.” Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka, Tom-2
14. Sh. Umirzaqova (2022) “Using language experience approach in training TFL.” Scientific Ideas Of Young Scientists | Pomysly Naukowe Mlodych Naukowcow Научные Идеи Молодых Ученых Tom-6, 76-79